

HMC Interactive - Notes

DATA SOURCE: <https://quest-fair-assessment.charite.de/>

Find in the third tab outputs with comments/recommendations from the tools.

Survey - Familiarity with FAIR assessment tools (19 participants):

How would you rate your familiarity with FAIR Data Principles? 19

> I am familiar with FAIR Data Principles

> I am familiar with the concept of automated FAIR assesment tools

Have you ever used a FAIR assessment tool? 19

If yes, please name the tool you used: 10 10

Most popular

Also prominent

Other responses

Tasks:

1. Create an overview of the FAIR assessment results for the principle.
Highlight key insights or any significant patterns or trends that catches your attention.
2. Which tool did score well in your Principle and for which Metrics?

Select one Metric for a detailed analysis that performed not so well in your opinion (examples provided in your Miro board)

3. What are the gaps in evaluation of this metric among available tools?
What does support your findings e.g. in code or tool's documentation?

F-UJI:

1. Tool landing page: <https://www.f-ujii.net/>
2. Code: <https://github.com/pangaea-data-publisher/fuji>
3. Docu: <https://zenodo.org/records/6461229>

FAIR Enough

1. Tool landing page: <https://fair-enough.semanticscience.org/>
2. Code: <https://github.com/MaastrichtU-IDS/fair-enough>
3. Docu: <https://github.com/FAIRMetrics/Metrics/tree/master/MaturityIndicators>

FAIR-Checker:

1. Tool landing page: <https://fair-checker.france-bioinformatique.fr/>
2. Code: <https://github.com/IFB-ElixirFr/fair-checker>
3. Docu: <https://fair-checker.france-bioinformatique.fr/docs/index.html>

Discussion notes:

Participation: 17 participants attended initially.

General observations on FAIR assessment and its purpose

- Purpose of FAIR scores:
 - FAIR principles aim for machine readability, not necessarily scientific value or quality.
 - Scores do not evaluate data content.
 - FAIR scores are not meaningful for all use cases; for example, high 'accessibility' may not align with user expectations.
 - FAIR is one of many guidelines, with parallels like FAIR for software (which does not assess code quality).
- Challenges with FAIR scoring:
 - Scores may be misinterpreted by researchers or third parties (e.g., funders) as indicators of being "good" or "bad".
 - Domains differ in resources and expectations, leading to variable FAIR outcomes.

- Overemphasis on automated scoring risks creating "*monster metrics*" similar to the JIF.

Current limitations and challenges

- Scope of FAIR Principles:
 - FAIR does not fully address the replication crisis or incentivize researchers struggling with time pressures.
 - Openness varies by field; some disciplines cannot share data freely.
 - Tools are less effective in evaluating complex or nuanced datasets.
- Automated FAIR tools:
 - Useful in specific areas like AI research where machine readability is key.
 - Limitations include inability to capture all aspects of FAIRness and potential misuse in evaluations.
 - Tools need to consider domain-specific challenges and corner cases.

Benefits to the research ecosystem:

- Encourages reuse of data and saves effort (e.g., easier access for PhD students).
- Can act as a starting point for improving data and metadata quality.
- Promotes community awareness and dialogue on data sharing and evaluation.

Practical recommendations and future steps

- For researchers and institutions:
 - Use automated tools carefully, as guidance rather than definitive measures.
 - Brief researchers on FAIR compliance and its practical benefits.
- For tool development and use:
 - Encourage feedback to developers to improve tools and address limitations.
 - Expand tools to better handle edge cases and domain-specific needs.
 - Avoid sole reliance on automated metrics; expert evaluation may provide complementary insights (despite challenges like resource intensity and potential biases).

General Best Practices:

- Choose FAIR tools carefully and evaluate what they measure.
- Raise awareness about limitations and potential misuse of metrics.
- Consider consolidating existing tools to reduce fragmentation.

Breakout-rooms discussions:

1. Group Accessible

board: <https://app.eraser.io/integration/gather/YvZqxoTnpiAdyNActable6>

overall observations

- general-purpose repositories scored higher in all three tools
- FAIR Checker has on average the highest scores → does it mean it is 'the best'?

gaps in evaluations and supportive arguments

- e.g. A1:
 - F-UJI measures only A1
 - but docu of F-UJI - as if mixed approach, which includes A1.2 and A2 into A1
- lacking precise docu documentation, e.g. FAIR Checker describes in A1.1 only HTTP, although HTTPs also successfully measured

other remarks and discussion

- why are we looking at these scoring numbers? what do they tell us? → is a high number reached with only "Interoperability" but missing "Findability" or "Accessibility" completely good or not good?
- the FAIR Principles are currently more human understandable than for machines → but the intended different
- how reliable are the tools if they have yet such an early dev stage?

2. Group Interoperable

board: <https://app.eraser.io/integration/gather/zk4VBA5UHxH7f5U4table2>

overall observations

- scores are low overall
- in particular for I3 and for disciplinary repositories
- FAIR-enough tends to report higher values for I3

individual metrics

- I1
 - formulation in the FAIR Data Principles is much more generic than the operationalization in F-UJI
- I2
 - automated FAIR assessment tools check for very specific requirements
 - resources that are well described but lack technical maturity score low; even for repositories with a high standing in their respective communities (GenBank, CCDC)
- I3

- discrepancies in the operationalization between tools: I3 in FAIR Enough seems more similar to I2 in F-UJI
- there are false positives and false negatives: cases where existing links to related resources are not detected, or other links are misinterpreted

other remarks

- **tools should be chosen after careful consideration**; be aware of how the FAIR Data Principles are operationalized in the tool
- **tools might benefit from 'catering' more to a specific discipline** - requirements could be defined more precisely, results might be more meaningful for users; but having scores be comparable across domains also has value
- **some repositories might not care about the scores they achieve in FAIR assessment tools, because they are highly reused in their disciplines**; but others might adapt their practices to improve their scores (if scores are used to evaluate the repositories)
- **much of the assessment seems to depend on the repository software**

3. Group Reusable

board: <https://app.eraser.io/workspace/gather:7hRwmKK6LkGEZs0Ntable6>

Which tool did score well:

- F-UJI created good scoring but the explanations for failures are poor
- FAIR Checker is similar to FAIR Enough with a different interface
- FAIR Enough scoring is worse than F-UJI, but the explanations are actually useful

What are the gaps in evaluation of this metric among available tools

- fair-enough.semantic-science.org doesn't check R1.3 but scores it, so the max score is 75%
- all tools recall W3 standard metadata keys from the websites, but use different parameter subsets (i.e. json, xml, binary or all)
- FAIR Enough & FAIR Checker based their score on the FAIR Principles (i.e. 3 subprinciples = 3 tests); F-UJI enlarge the amount of categories (i.e. 3 principles end up in 3-5 tests -> sum up as %)

What does support your findings

- Quote F-UJI docs: "*The implementation ... therefore verifies the presence of data content descriptors in appropriate fields of metadata records ... validates the values of the descriptors against the actual data file. Apache Tika is here used for content analysis.*"

Do you have other remarks

- if a tool can't read a file format it scores it as "fail" even if its a zip-archive
- 100% FAIR shouldn't be possible like a perfect 1 correlation because of natural noise and biases

General remarks

- should there be "disciplinary" FAIR-principles, e.g. medical FAIR Principles (for sensitive datasets)
- are automated tools useful for disciplinary repositories, if they cannot handle discipline-specific metadata standards like humans can?
- how do we rate quality? the completeness of filled out fields is not automatically high quality
- promote high quality datasets to create incentives
- relevance of data stewards and metadata & data management governance
- pressure comes from publication, where publishing data is necessary (e.g. field of neuroscience)
- not just FAIR 'yes' vs. FAIR 'no', but how we try to become as FAIR as possible